

Title: Life Cycle Assessment as a decision support tool for the implementation of circular economy and decarbonization strategies in the steel industry

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Abstract

The assessment of environmental sustainability in the steel sector is attracting an increasing interest in European policies [1], as well as research projects and initiatives [2]. One of the most widely used methodologies to quantify the potential environmental impacts of the steelmaking industry is Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), which has a long history of application in the sector, e.g. [3, 4, 5]. More recently, the LCA methodology has also been used to support the investigation of circular economy (CE) and decarbonization strategies in steel production and recycling, see [6] and [7], respectively.

According to Rieger et al. [8], there are three main options to implement CE strategies in the steel sector: i) enhancing steel recycling, ii) valorising steelmaking residues (e.g. dust, slags, foundry sands, and flue gases), and iii) using secondary sources from non-steel sectors (e.g. carbon sources, reducing agents). In relation to the first option (enhancing steel recycling), steel and iron scraps can be used to produce secondary steel in electric arc furnaces (EAFs) as a more environmentally friendly alternative to primary steelmaking plants like blast furnaces (BF) and basic oxygen furnaces (BOF) [9]. In relation to the second option, several steelmaking residues such as dust and slags contain valuable metals (e.g. zinc) to be recovered and reintegrated into the metallurgical industry thus avoiding the environmental impacts of further virgin materials extraction and processes [10]. Finally, some of these residues (e.g. slags and foundry sands) are also suitable to be used in other industrial sectors, such as the production of construction materials like cement or asphalt, therefore supporting industrial symbiosis [11].

According to Suer et al. [7] breakthrough technologies for a decarbonized steel production are available, but as interim scenarios, modifications of the BF related steel production route should be used, like hydrogen injection into the BF or use of pre-reduced iron ores in the BF. However, the decarbonization cannot be fulfilled completely within the BF route, therefore the steel production via direct reduction (DR) plants is also promising. Moreover, DR plants in combination with electrical melting offer the opportunity to minimize GHG (Greenhouse Gases) emissions.

It is acknowledged that there is an increasing interest in the steelmaking industry in outlining the potential of LCA as a useful tool for the evaluation of the environmental performances of alternative CE and decarbonisation strategies, as outlined by a recent review of the application of LCA to CE in steelmaking industry [12]. In this context, the aim of this contribution is to present two real-world research projects funded by the European Union in the context of the Horizon Europe programme, where the LCA methodology is actively used to guide the decision-making process towards the implementation of the most effective CE and decarbonization strategies in relation to future steel production targeting reduced environmental impacts.

ALCHIMIA project

ALCHIMIA “Data and decentralized Artificial intelligence for a competitive and green European metallurgy industry” is an European project funded by the Horizon Europe programme. The project aims to develop methodologies for the environmental optimization of steelmaking processes through the application of digital technologies based on Artificial Intelligence techniques (<https://alchimia-project.eu/>). In three of the case studies considered in the ALCHIMIA project, LCA is used to optimize the scraps mix and the energy consumption flows based on 3 EAF steelmaking plants owned by CELSA Group [13]. The fourth case study refers to the optimization of the production of automotive components in an Italian foundry that is engaged in the improvement of the resource efficiency of the production line (Fonderia di Torbole, FdT) [14]. A list of the case studies considered in ALCHIMIA project and key aspects of the LCA methodology (functional unit, system boundaries) are listed in Table 1.

Table 1. List of case studies considered in ALCHIMIA project and use of LCA methodology

Case study n#	Company	Geography	Functional unit	System boundaries
1	CELSA	France	1 ton of steel	Cradle to Gate
2	CELSA	Spain	1 ton of steel	Cradle to Gate
3	CELSA	Poland	1 ton of steel	Cradle to Gate
4	FDT	Italy	1 ton of steel components	Cradle to Gate

A graphical illustration of the use of LCA to support the implementation of CE strategies in CELSA France case study is presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1. System boundaries of the CELSA France case study with indication of main Circular Economy (CE) strategies investigated.

The focus in the ALCHIMIA project is primarily on the production of secondary steel from scraps. Therefore, a key aspect to be analysed is related to steel quality issues. Indeed, cleaning scraps operations during pre-treatment allows an increase in the quality of scraps and it overall reduces the energy consumption of steel foundries by 45% [9]. Moreover, the recovery of valuable materials from slags and dust represents another effective CE strategy, since relevant environmental benefits can be obtained through the recovery of chromium [10] and zinc [15]. On the other side steel slags are also suitable to produce high-quality direct reduction iron [16]. To optimize the input of materials and energy consumption a mathematic optimization tool is expected to be developed within the ALCHIMIA project.

GreenHeatEAF project

The EU-funded project entitled “Gradual Integration of REnewable carbon and alternative non-carbon Energy sources and modular HEATling technologies in EAF for progressive CO₂ decrease – GreenHeatEAF” aims at investigating the replacement of natural gas and other fossil energy sources with hydrogen or renewable carbon sources (e.g. biochar) in EAF. In addition, technologies to re-optimize the heating management with maximum heat recovery from off-gas and slag are explored. Coupling pilot tests with digital applications constitutes the strength of GreenHeatEAF (<https://www.estep.eu/clean-steel-partnership/list-of-csp-projects/greenheateaf/project-overview/>).

LCA and Life Cycle Costing (LCC) methods are used in the GreenHeatEAF project (WP4) to assess the environmental and economic performance of the melting process to evaluate the impact after the implementation of developed scenarios (integration of non-carbon gases, renewable C-sources and modular heating technologies in steelworks) and compare to a baseline scenario.

Three main decarbonization strategies are investigated within the GreenHeatEAF project:

- Integration of non-fossil gases flows (as part of WP1), which test the use of hydrogen in different blends;
- Fossil C-sources replacement with biomass/biochar (as part of WP2);
- Modular and alternative heat recovery (as part of WP1 and WP3), through off-gas or slags.

A schematization of the concept implemented in the GreenHeatEAF project is presented in Figure 2.

Figure 2. Overview of key elements in the GreenHeatEAF. Source: <https://www.estep.eu/clean-steel-partnership/list-of-csp-projects/greenheateaf/project-overview/>

A list of the case studies to be analysed within the GreenHeatEAF project is reported in Table 2.

Table 2. Table title (centered)

Case study n#	Company	Geography	Functional unit	Baseline technology
1	SSAB	Sweden	1 ton of steel	BOF-BF
2	Sidenor	Spain	1 ton of steel	EAF - scrap route batch EAF
3	CELSA Nordic	Poland	1 ton of steel	EAF - Scrap route Consteeel
4	Hoganas	Sweden	1 ton of steel	EAF - Scrap route batch

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References

- [1] European Steel Technology Platform (ESTEP) “Clean Steel Partnership Roadmap. 2020”. Available online: <https://www.estep.eu/assets/Uploads/200715-CSP-Roadmap-version-public-consultation.pdf> (accessed on 8 April 2024) (2020)
- [2] Andreotti M., Brondi C., Micillo D., Zevenhoven R., Rieger J., Jo A., Hettinger A.L., Bollen J., Malfa E., Trevisan C., Peters K., Snaet D., Ballarino A., “SDGs in the EU Steel Sector: A Critical Review of Sustainability Initiatives and Approaches”. *Sustainability (Switzerland)* 15, 7521 (2023)
- [3] Andersson G., Ponzio A., Gauffin A., Axelsson H., Nilson G., “Sustainable steel production–Swedish initiative to ‘close the loop.’ *Transactions of the Institutions of Mining and Metallurgy*”, Section C: Mineral Processing and Extractive Metallurgy 126, 81–88, (2017)
- [4] Renzulli P.A., Notarnicola B., Tassielli G., Arcese G., Di Capua R., “Life cycle assessment of steel produced in an Italian integrated steel mill”. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 8, 719., (2016)
- [5] Mitterpach J., Hroncová E., Ladomerský J., Balco K., “Environmental analysis of waste foundry sand via life cycle assessment”. *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* 24, 3153–3162., (2017)
- [6] Colla V., Branca T.A., Pietruck R., Wölfelschneider S., Morillon A., Algermissen D., Rosendahl S., Granbom H., Martin, U., Snaet D., “Future Research and Developments on Reuse and Recycling of Steelmaking By-Products”. *Metals (Basel)*, 13, 676., (2023)
- [7] Suer J., Traverso M., Jäger N., “Review of Life Cycle Assessments for Steel and Environmental Analysis of Future Steel Production Scenarios”. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 14, 14131., (2022)
- [8] Rieger J., Colla V., Matino I., Branca T.A., Stubbe G., Panizza A., Brondi C., Falsafi M., Hage J., Wang X., Voraberger B., Fenzl T., Masaguer V., Faraci E.L., Di Sante, L., Cirilli F., Loose F., Thaler C., Soto A., Frittella P., Foglio G., Di Cecca C., Tellaroli M., Corbella M., Guzzon M., Malfa E., Morillon A., Algermissen D., Peters K., Snaet D., “Residue valorization in the iron and steel industries: Sustainable solutions for a cleaner and more competitive future Europe.” *Metals (Basel)*, 11, 1202., (2021)
- [9] Haupt M., Vadenbo C., Zeltner C., Hellweg S., “Influence of Input-Scrap Quality on the Environmental Impact of Secondary Steel Production” *Journal of Industrial Ecology* 21, 391–401. (2017)
- [10] Buyle M., Maes B., Van Passel S., Boonen K., Vercalsteren A., Audenaert A., “Ex-ante LCA of emerging carbon steel slag treatment technologies: Fast forwarding lab observations to industrial-scale production.” *Journal of Cleaner Production* 313, 127921., (2021)
- [11] Di Maria A., Salman M., Dubois M., Van Acker K., “Life cycle assessment to evaluate the environmental performance of new construction material from stainless steel slag”. *International Journal of Life Cycle Assessment* 23, 2091–2109., (2018)
- [12] Rossi F, Niero M., Frey, M, “Application of LCA to circular economy strategies in steelmaking industry: state-of-the-art and recommendations. In *Proceedings of XVIII Convegno dell’Associazione Rete Italiana LCA “LIFE CYCLE THINKING A SUPPORTO DI MODELLI DI PRODUZIONE E DI CONSUMO SOSTENIBILI”* 3-7 July 2024 Pescara, Italy (under review)
- [13] CELSA Group, “Sustainability Report”, viewed 11 Mar 2024, <https://www.celsagroup.com/en/sustainability-report-celsa-group/> (2022)
- [14] EF Group, 2021. “The Fonderia di Torbole Sustainability Report”, viewed 11 Mar 2024, <https://www.ef-group.it/en/the-fonderia-di-torbole-sustainability-report> (2021)
- [15] Ng K.S., Head I., Premier G.C., Scott K., Yu E., Lloyd J., Sadhukhan J., “A multilevel sustainability analysis of zinc recovery from wastes”. *Resources Conservation and Recycling* 113, 88–105. (2016)
- [16] Nurdawati A., Zaini I.N., Wei W., Gyllenram R., Yang W., Samuelsson P., “Towards fossil-free steel: Life cycle assessment of biosyngas-based direct reduced iron (DRI) production process “. *J Cleaner Production* 393. (2023)